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Diversifying The Teaching of Entrepreneurship Education In Public Universities For Self Employment: The Business Educator's Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on diversifying the teaching of Entrepreneurship Education in public universities for self employment the Business Educator's Perspective. The study saw a paradigm shift from what was formerly taught in the universities in Nigeria. In recent years, there has been need to inculcate into the curriculum, courses related to entrepreneurship programme. Due to the current political, economic, and social influence of the global economic meltdown, many countries of the world have resulted to diversify on their domestic economy so as to promote a sustainable domestic economy that will be moderately resistant from the economic and financial struggles that may arise in the future. Major concepts were reviewed in this study which include; diversity, entrepreneurial education, self-employment, issue on material resource, issue on talent management benefits of diversity. The study concluded that Entrepreneurial Education with the use of material resource provision and talent management will enhance self-employment of Business Education students upon graduation. The study suggested that University authorities should provide teaching staff with needed resources for Entrepreneurial Education and Entrepreneurial Education should be funded by all stake holders for self-employment in Rivers State.

Keywords: Diversify, Entrepreneurship, Self-Employment, Resource, Talent Management

INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential tool for personal, social and economic development. Every country, including the developing ones believes education to be a vehicle with which they can use to achieve their manpower needs. The purpose of education in most developing nations like Nigeria has been conceived and perceived as that of developing the individual and the nation at large. This belief has resulted to a high level of commitment to educational goals by every tier of government considering its importance, benefits and contributions in the society. Education is a key ingredient to the growth and development of every nation and society.

Entrepreneurship education is the process of creating wealth through risk taking. It is the act of venturing into business for the main purpose of maximising wealth. Onuoha (2016) defined it as the practice of starting new organizations or revitalizing mature organizations, particularly new businesses generally in response to identified opportunities. An entrepreneur is an individual who takes risks, pools his resources together and invests in a business for the main purpose of making profit. No person or organization

ventures into business just for the sake of it. They are there to make profit and so, they try all avenues to ensure that their capital is judiciously used to give them the much needed profit they need.

In universities in Nigeria, there has been a paradigm shift from what was formerly taught in the curriculum. In recent years, there has been a need to inculcate into the curriculum, courses related to entrepreneur. In most universities in Nigeria, various entrepreneurial courses are being taught to students to equip them with the necessary tools of becoming self-reliant and independent after graduation. These courses are being taught to shape the minds of the undergraduates in order for them not to depend solely on the government, but also to be creators of jobs. There are needs for adequate entrepreneurial resources such as human, material and financial resources for proper implementation that will enhance business education students' interest for self-employment upon graduation from universities in Rivers State. Due to the current political, economic, and social influence of the global economic meltdown, many countries of the world have resulted to look on their domestic economy so as to promote a sustainable domestic economy that will be moderately resistant from the economic and financial strangling that may try to reoccur in the future. Nigeria has a history of post-colonial agrarian economy and is now heavily dependent on the oil and gas sector economy. Efforts are now being made to diversify the economy by investing for example in agriculture and the manufacturing sector. However, entrepreneurship-led development strategies are now being emphasised because they have proven successful in several Less Developed Countries (LCDs).

Entrepreneurship involves innovation; bringing something new and unique to a market that does not exist before. Some experts and writers are of the view that entrepreneurship is a service rendered by anyone who starts a new business. Furthermore, any person who has the zeal and ability to discover and evaluate opportunities, generate resources and takes steps towards taking advantage of such opportunities can become an entrepreneur. Entrepreneurial education is the type of education designed to change the orientation and attitude of the recipients and the process will equip them with the skills and knowledge to enable them start and manage a business. It aims at developing the requisite entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, competencies, and disposition that will predispose the individual to be a driving force in managing a business (Agu, 2016). On the other hand, entrepreneurial education can be said to focus on developing understanding and capacity for pursuit of entrepreneurial behaviours, skills and attitudes in widely different contexts. This type of education is open to all and not exclusively the domain of the some self-acclaimed business gurus (Akpomi, 2013).

In Rivers State, there are students otherwise known as business education students undertaking courses in entrepreneurial education. These students are being taught so that they can also be independent and create jobs for themselves. There are three public universities in Rivers state. These are the University of Port Harcourt, located at Choba, Rivers State University, located at Nkpolu-Oroworukwo and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, located at Rumuolumeni. These universities have entrepreneurial education courses taught both at the undergraduate and post-graduate levels. It is very pertinent to note that undergraduate students in these universities have the interest for self-employment.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurial education has been defined as a collection of formalized teachings that informs, trains, and educates anyone interested in participating in socio-economic development through a project to promote entrepreneurship awareness, business creation, or small business development (Peters, 2016). Entrepreneurial education has the mandate to equip the youth with functional =knowledge and skill to build up their character, attitude and vision. It has vital role in developing eco-system that promotes innovation. It provides the basis for innovation, creating a value system, developing entrepreneurial culture which drives wealth creation and gives further push to innovations. It provides the opportunity and knowledge for individuals to create wealth for themselves through functional skills and creativity. Entrepreneurial education equips the individual with the ideas and competence, needed to create value in the society and make wealth.

Entrepreneurial education seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. In other words, it is a competency-based

education that focuses on knowledge and skills. Aderinwale in Hisrich (2017) further described entrepreneurial education as the one that transverse the length of business formation, management, diversification and growth and ongoing process that equip entrepreneurs (students) with entrepreneurial skills. Entrepreneurship has become a powerful tool for creating jobs and improving economic power in the labour market and economy as a whole. Moreover, with the advent of the fourth industrial revolution, a variety of competencies such as creativity, innovation, and agility are required for start-ups.

In Nigeria, unemployment and youth restiveness is a major problem that has inundated the country into an economic crisis that over the years has been dwindling. The rate of youth restiveness and unemployment is overwhelming and increasing. Recently, the country has been named the world's poorest country with the highest poverty rate. Many students who later graduate are sent into the society to look for jobs that are rarely available. Most departments, agencies, ministries and parastatals are money making centres where people are asked to pay huge sums of money before given government jobs. Most of these agencies only employ and recruit individuals based on connections and how much they know them (Asagha, 2014).

The entrepreneurial Education has been defined as a collection of formalized teachings that educate anyone interested in business creation (Bechard & Toulouse, 2018). The entrepreneurial education can trigger the entrepreneurial initiatives by enhancing entrepreneurial mind-set among the students (Lubis, 2014). A study conducted on college students in China conclude that entrepreneurial education should be included in colleges and universities' reform and development plan, personnel training system, and teaching evaluation index system.

Entrepreneurial Education seeks to inculcate in individuals, especially students, the zeal to acquire knowledge in business that will make them independent. All the skills, knowledge and information is taught in schools where entrepreneurial education is instituted thereby, shifting the focus of the child from white collar jobs to fending for themselves after graduation. It is ok to work in government parastatals, but the tides are changing. Not everyone will have white collar jobs or earn from the government coffers. Also, the government jobs are no forthcoming, hence, the need to educate students in tertiary education on how to be self- employed. Entrepreneurial education has the following benefits (Asagha, 2014):

1. It enables students to acquire fresh and new information on entrepreneur, outside their usual core subjects.
2. It motivates students to become self-employed upon graduation.
3. It revives the spirit of independence amongst students.
4. It helps create jobs for students even while in school.
5. It reduces the rate of unemployment and youth restiveness in any society
6. It equips one for the future ahead and how to handle and cope with challenges

Entrepreneurship is regarded by most countries to be the panacea to unemployment and poverty reduction. Poverty and unemployment causes the youths of every nation to become idle and makes them to engage in illegal things, as the saying goes, "an idle man is the devil's workshop". Therefore, the aim of entrepreneurial education is to engage the youth in a meaningful way, thereby, causing higher institution graduates to be able to create their own jobs after leaving formal education. Thus, the teaching of entrepreneurial education is not an end itself, but a means to an end. Entrepreneurial education is a purposeful intervention by an educator in the life of the learner to impart entrepreneurial qualities and skills to enable the learner to survive in the world of business.

Entrepreneurship is the process of establishing a new firm, taking risk and making profit in the process. Entrepreneurship or business enterprises refers to a group of skills, which includes the ability to combine land, labour and capital in the most efficient way, the willingness to run the risk of the business failure and the creativity required to invent new products and new ways to market them. Entrepreneurship can be considered a special type of human resources. Entrepreneurship is the act or process of getting into and managing your own business enterprises. This involves any form of innovation that has a bearing on the welfare of the firm. Entrepreneurship is a process, while an entrepreneur is one who actively controls

the whole process of entrepreneurship. In the process of entrepreneurship, the entrepreneur has to have a foresight and should be willing to take risks.

Thomas and Mueller (2020) opined that skills and ideas required for successful entrepreneurship are innovation and ability to be creative to generate new ideas for a business venture. An entrepreneur must have the quality of leadership and a strong sense of unified teamwork to gain maximum benefit. It is very pertinent to know that what is very necessary for any person that wants to establish an enterprise is creativity and creative ideas.

The meaning of entrepreneurship involves an entrepreneur who takes action to make a change in the world. He sees opportunities and utilizes them. Once identified, the entrepreneur pools resources together, takes risks and opens up a business, for the sole aim of making profit. Whether to start up a business, solve a problem that many struggle with each day, bring people together in a way no one has before, or build something revolutionary that advances society, they all have one thing in common: action. An entrepreneur is a person who sets up a business with the aim to make a profit. Entrepreneurship is the act of creating a business or businesses while building and scaling it to generate a profit. Entrepreneurs all over the world have traits that make them excel in business which are seen in (Thomas & Mueller, 2020):

1. Self-Motivation
2. Understanding what to offer
3. Risk Taking
4. Networking skills
5. Basic Money Management Skills and Knowledge
6. Flexibility
7. Passion

Concept of Self-employment

Self employment is a process of pursuing careers in business creation and other related fields (Galvão, Ferreira & Marques, 2018). According to Toma, Grigore and Marinescu (2014), self employment generally considers how, why and when, opportunities are recognised, created and put to use. Thus, Self employment is commonly considered as the 'discovery and exploitation of opportunities'. In recent times, entrepreneurship and innovation seem to be the direction followed by different developed nations. For instance, the 2017 report of Global Entrepreneurship Index shows that the first ten well-performing nations in terms of entrepreneurship are developed nations (The Entrepreneurship and Development Institute, 2018). This gives a clue to the influence of entrepreneurship among other factors on the economic development and standard of developed nations across continents of the world.

This is ascertained based on the works of Light and Bhachu (2017) who state that entrepreneurship makes both societies in which it is practiced and the entrepreneurs better. This process is described as productive entrepreneurship. However, when entrepreneurship makes entrepreneurs better and leaves the society in a worse state, it is described as unproductive and destructive entrepreneurship. Suffice to state that entrepreneurship can be 'productive' or 'destructive'. By extension, the form of entrepreneurship commonly practiced in developed nations of the world will be regarded as productive since it has contributed to enhancing the standard of the economy, whereas, the form of entrepreneurship practiced in many developing nations of the world may be considered as unproductive or destructive, because, it has left some societies worse off, yet enriching many entrepreneurs. On the other hand, rural environments are expected to be developed through various

Concept of Diversity

Hisrich (2017) opined that diversity is recognising, respecting and valuing differences based on ethnicity, gender, age, race, religion, disability and sexual orientation. It also includes an infinite range of individual unique characteristics and experiences, such as communication style, career path, life experience, educational background, geographic location, income level, marital status, parental status and other variables that influence personal perspectives (Shane, 2017).

Diversity is acceptance of respect for the overall human characteristics in the socio-economic, cultural and historical contexts as well as beliefs. Diversity is about what makes each of us unique and includes our backgrounds, personality, life experiences and beliefs, all of the things that make us who we are. It is a combination of our differences that shape our view of the world, our perspective and our approach.

Inclusion occurs when people feel, and are, valued and respected. Regardless of their personal characteristic or circumstance. According to Peters (2016) inclusion helps people to;

- have the opportunity to fulfil their individual and combined potential
- have access to opportunities and resources
- can contribute their personal best in every encounter
- can contribute their perspectives and talents to improve their organisation
- can bring far more of themselves to their jobs
- have a sense of belonging.

Equal opportunity means that every person can participate freely and equally in areas of public life such as in the workplace, in education, or in accessing goods and services without disadvantage or less favourable treatment due to their unique attributes. Everyone in the workplace has rights and responsibilities under equal opportunity and anti-discrimination legislation to prevent discrimination, harassment, vilification or victimization. Equal opportunity is an integral part of the employment life cycle applicable to recruitment, retention, performance management, promotion, talent identification, succession planning, remuneration, professional development and end of employment (Ojelede, 2018).

Therefore, diversifying the teaching of Entrepreneurship Education involves meeting the needs of diverse learners as the responsibility of educators. Many teachers have been committed to making sure that all students receive an equal and adequate education. But it's figuring out *how* to provide this that's the tricky part. There are many ways educators can diversify the teaching of Entrepreneurship Education. According to Ojelede (2018) these are;

Make an Individualized education plans (IEP) cheat sheet

Individualized education plans (IEP) are lengthy, detailed documents showing what should be done to help individual learners. This saves the time of going back to old topics and repeating topic. Doing so will allow teachers to store reminders about important special education for a student on a single page.

Encourage active learning

Most educators have created at least one lesson where they thought, then, they took it into the classroom, and the students either didn't get it or wouldn't participate. This demonstrates a teaching fact that should be shared with all. It can be challenging to keep students engaged and actively involved. This is especially true for students who struggle with learning, speak English as a second language, or have trouble focusing. According to Lubis (2014), the solution is to incorporate active learning strategies to teach diverse learners such as;

- Group learning
- Case-based learning
- Group discussions and talk-and-turns
- One-minute papers and one-sentence summaries
- Demonstrations and memory matrixes

Embrace small group and learning stations

This involves dividing class into small groups for every lesson. Teachers should consider including centers and small group activities into their weekly routine in some way because it:

1. Helps all learners, especially diverse learners, by addressing knowledge gaps
2. Promotes collaboration and communication among students
3. Gives you more opportunities for feedback
4. Encourages independent learning

Group by learning style, not ability

So, how should we group students? I've found that using mixed-ability groups can promote learning, especially when students get the opportunity to coach or teach their peers' An extension of this is to place

students who learn in similar ways together, visual learners with visual learners, auditory with auditory, etc. Doing so can make a huge difference during small-group instruction.

Promote project-based learning

Ogbodo (2015), while you are differentiating your teaching, consider project-based learning (PBL). Project-based learning is not a summative assessment; it is a way of helping students understand what is being taught through hands-on methods. During PBL activities, students work together to solve real-world problems by coming up with solutions together. The real ingredients of project-based learning activities used to teach diverse learners are:

- The academic content itself (the topic you're teaching)
- Real-world scenarios that make the material more relevant
- A sense of purpose (end goal)
- Opportunities to practice collaboration
- 21st-century skills
- Student-focused activities with ample choice
- Opportunities for self-reflection

Incorporate education technology as adaptive learning tools

Another suggestion for finding creative ways to teach students is to incorporate ed-tech and adaptive learning tools. Kaur (2019) opined that there are many technologies designed for certain students, these include:

- Plickers, free card activities for formative assessment
- Wordsinasenten-ce.com to help students understand vocabulary in context
- Class craft for game-based classroom management options, like topic review framed as Boss Battles
- Book Creator as an alternative assessment
- Google Keep for electronic note-taking and organization

Provide alternative testing options

One final suggestion is to find alternative testing avenues for individual learners (if allowed) or the class as a whole. The fact that we traditionally test on paper doesn't mean that it's the only acceptable way. Instead, you should differentiate your approach by allowing students to answer orally, through drawings (pictures), and with the use of their notes. Doing a quick Google search for "alternative assessments" will bring up tons of creative testing ideas for every type of student. This will allow you to evaluate your students better and improve your own teaching (Onuoha, 2016).

Issues and Challenges on Material Resource to Diversify Teaching of Entrepreneurship

The concept of material resources is a contemporary idea which before now, had been known as school facilities. Material resources as a concept have been viewed from different perspectives by different school of thoughts in educational system. Some school of thoughts expressed their view by defined material resources as building, equipment, text books including the surrounding where teaching and learning take place. The material resources include all permanent and semi-permanent structure in the school. Ololube (2013) defined material resources as those things used in the school such as: school, building, ground equipment, lawns and parts, furniture, fields, laboratories, libraries, tools and machines and chalk boards.

Lawanson and Gede (2019) defined material resources comprehensively as: All facilities needed for the takeoff and sustenance of a school. All facilities includes buildings, ground, land, all school accessory apart from human being is referred to material resources. The adequacy of material resources which in other words means the sufficiency and quality of material resources environment is of utmost importance. Also the provision of material resources in any school is not negotiable but necessity. This will go a long way in making teaching and learning process progressive. There has been little or no consideration for the effect the material resources would have on the teaching-learning situation and for the achievement of the

laid down goals. It is not uncommon to find students sit down on windows to receive instruction and it is common to find as many as seventy students in a class meant to accommodate forty students. Most schools are deficient in audiovisual materials that will aid teaching and learning. The result of these is that there exists little or no interaction between the teacher and the learner.

Educational planners, however, are convinced of the importance of good physical facility planning in the development of an efficient and effective educational programme in all sector of the educational programme in all sector of the educational system. A well planned and articulated school will not only enhance good teaching practices but also will facilitate learning. There is absolute need of planning the school buildings and facilities because such planning will enhance the achievement of the aims and objectives for which the school is established. School buildings and educational goals are closely related and interwoven. In other words, educational buildings and facilities must help to achieve the purpose for which the school is established.

Provision and utilization of quality facilities in school stimulates students interest to study hard. When school environment is attractive and fascinating it arouses students to invite their friends for programmes such as inter-house sports competitions, quiz, debate competition and other educational programmes. It also gives teachers comfort to perform credibly and impart the right concepts to students. Any of these resources must be managed by an experience teacher. Conversely, any facility in school A should also be the same in school B, because it is disheartening that some schools will receive formidable and educating facilities and equipments such as computers, gadgets, school buses, library and its materials, books and printed materials, laboratory and its equipments, projectors, wireless speakers, and other instructional media (IMs), while others have none. Equal distribution/allocation of these facilities/equipments contributes immensely to the learning of the child in school. Good school/working environment also contributes greatly to sustainable academic achievement of students. Asagha (2014) asserted that good working environment will motivate staff to perform effectively in order to achieve desired set goals for school or other organizations outside the school.

He also asserts that adequate provision of housing and offices is a serious matter for staff in most schools. It implies that, facilitation of such magnitude contributes to the improvement of school goals. Invariably, a situation whereby other staff are given good accommodation and well equipped offices bias will definitely set in and the end result will be unseriousness in lesson planning; i.e. planning and writing lesson note without researching effectively, deteriorate in lesson presentation, absenteeism on the increase, teaching without practical demonstration, and plans to leave the job for another will set in; while student's suffer academic failure.

Provision of physical and material resources for students and teachers utilization needs to be distributed equally to all schools without favouring the urban schools against rural schools. Physical facilities are very significant to the well-being of personnel of the school. Nweake (2017) opined that, it is putting together of facilities to protect the physical well-being of individual associated with school. Agabi (2017) opined that it contributes meaningfully to the teaching-learning process. However, if schools can receive functional facilities, conducive and attractive school environment and instructional media, computer gadgets, teaching staff absenteeism and other attributes of a fallen school will be effaced drastically. This is the reason Kpee (2014) Material resource planning as take-off and sustenance of a school. It keeps the school going, lively and sustains academics by arousing students to be competitive in challenging one another academically. Since the amalgamation of the northern and southern protectorate in 1914, Nigeria has continued to swim in an ocean of ethnic politics. Politics comes to play in everything as it concerns Nigerians. Merits are always repudiated for ethnicity and other forms of favour. Allocation of resources in educational system is based on ethnicity which ends up putting a square peg in a round hole. This method forms basis for inequality and brings about fallen standard of education as students are affected by it. This method of allocation of teaching staff sets huge imbalanced study opportunities to some schools.

The material resource can be defined as the school environment and everything within it needed for effective teaching and learning process. This includes the permanent and non-permanent structures as well as the facilities and equipment such as building, furniture, vehicles, laboratories, libraries,

playground, books furniture etc. Ogbodo, (2015) referred to material resource as the facilities of education that includes school building (classrooms, assembly halls, laboratories and workshop, libraries etc) teaching aids and devices such as modern educational hardware and their software in the form of magnetic tapes and films.

Before modernization in the educational system, teachers met their students under trees using the tree shade as shelter. In recent times, these material resources are seen in the school compound for effective teaching and learning but how they are utilized is a major concern in the educational system. Ojelede (2018) stated that material resources comprise the school site and structure that have been put place to aid effective teaching and learning in the school system. It is therefore, almost impossible for teachers to record a perceived high level of performance if the things required for teaching and learning are not put in place. In the same vein, Ajayi (2017) upheld that high level of students learning outcome may not be guaranteed where material resources such as school site planning and structural space planning, administrate space planning.

Material resources are made up of the crucial components and structures essential for any worthwhile educational system to perform successfully and achieve the goal for which it was established in the first instance (Alimi, Ehinola & Alabi, 2017). A school that has adequate instructional materials is likely to post or record better grades than a school which has poor quality physical resources. Juma (2019) related performance in examination to the condition of teaching and learning resources in schools. He records that students from poor backgrounds perform poorly in the examinations because the poor are often in areas where schools are seriously deprived of vital facilities. The lack of basic facilities like laboratories has compromised the teaching of science subject topics that are meant to be taught practically are taught theoretically as part of adoptive mechanism by teachers due to inadequate resources to enable effective teaching of the same; this ends up limiting the academic performance and opportunities of student. If quality education is to be maintained, then provision, utilization and maintenance of the material resource must not be underemphasized, as effective learning cannot be achieved in the absence of the essential materials needed for its occurrence.

The major task of every educational personnel is to utilize all available educational resources optimally to achieve targeted educational goals. It is not out of place to state that there is a connection between the material resource and the academic achievement of students. That is why parents or guardians who are aware of this fact go in search of well-equipped schools with sophisticated infrastructural capabilities for their children and ward. The school pant is directly or indirectly connected to the school curriculum. Mgbodile (2016) described material resource as the space interpretation of the school curriculum. It therefore implies that the school academic activities should strongly have an influence on the schools architectural design hence the curriculum should be developed before the architectural design. Hisrich (2017) explained utilization as making use of available services or resources at the individual's disposal. These resources within the educational sector include the facilities, equipment and experienced personnel. Olagunju and Abiona (2017) opined that the process of managing and organizing resources is resource utilization. Tertiary institution is the form of education children receive after primary education before tertiary level. In other words, it is the level of education after the primary or basic level of education. Material resource consists of infrastructural facilities and equipment within the school (Ogundele, Sambo & Bwoi, 2015).

Depending on the availability of funds and size of the project, among some other factors, the planning, design, and construction of a school facility may take two to four years but the management of it lasts as long as the facility does. It is the duty of the school head to ensure that the material resources is ready for use when due and that it is correctly used for the purpose for which it is meant. This is necessary in order to prevent any disruption of the educational programme.

Issues and Challenges on Talent Management to Diversify Teaching of Entrepreneurship

In recent times, there has been a general belief that students who graduate from the university are unemployable as a result of the lack of skills, knowledge and attitude needed for contributing to the

growth and development of their society. This has become worrisome because the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) stated through the national policy on education that university education is saddled with the responsibility of grooming students who will contribute to the growth and development of their society through the development of their abilities and skills. If students will contribute to the growth of their immediate environment, there is need to groom these students to be self reliant. This is because self reliance will enable these students to be able to contribute to personal and societal growth and development unaided. Kaur (2019) stated that self reliance is a strong belief in one's worth and the feeling of being satisfied with oneself and abilities. It is the ability to tackle existing problems personally without depending on others. Therefore, when students are trained to be self reliant, they can confidently make meaningful progress in any area of life. Similarly,

Self reliant students are usually outstanding both in and outside the classroom if properly guided. Paso, Chantarasombat and Tirasiravech (2017) noted that students self reliance has different aspects which includes; educational, social features and economics. This means that a self reliant student has the capacity to succeed both educationally, economically and socially and this is needed to achieve personal ambition and contribute to the society. However, if students will become self reliant, their abilities and skills especially their talents must be properly harnessed by their instructors. There are different activities involved in the process of talent management which teachers must familiarize with to develop the independence of their students. Agbaeze, Monyei and Agu (2017) pointed out that talent management strategies are of different dimensions such as workforce planning, recruitment, on boarding new hires, training and development, coaching, high performance development, rewards and recognition, succession planning, record keeping reporting and analysis, culture and values.

Furthermore, Lewis and Heckman as cited in Aibieyi and Henry (2015) also asserted that "talent management involves identifying mission-critical values, competencies and talents needed in the current and future work force; clarifying the methods that will be used to recruit, hire, develop, manage and retain high performing workforce. Teachers in the university therefore have a lot of responsibilities in the management of the talent of their students to guide them towards becoming self reliant. The success of university students to contribute to their own economic and educational independence depends on the extent to which their talents are being managed. Students will continue to be a burden on the society and themselves if their innate abilities are not identified and managed. Therefore, university teachers have responsibility in the management of their students as this holds the key to the self reliance of their students.

Prospect and Benefits of Diversifying Teaching of Entrepreneurship Education

Diversity is very important. Many graduates are periodically churned out of the university and many of them are unemployed due to lack of jobs. These graduates seek government jobs and prefer working either at the federal or state level. Many of them do not have the zeal or will power for business or entrepreneurial aspirations. But the truth is that entrepreneurship seems to be the only proper way out of the seemingly scarcity of jobs. It has been discovered that hunger and poverty, together with unemployment has separated many families and led to the increase in crime rate in the country. This had led to the emergence and introduction of entrepreneurial education in universities, in order for students to become independent and create jobs after graduation (Ogundele, Sambo & Bwoi, 2015).

Therefore, most institutions currently provide entrepreneurial training programs with the belief that the importance of entrepreneurship and the knowledge and skills needed to become an entrepreneur can be taught, and the proportion of policy support toward entrepreneurial education has been increasing in many countries around the world. Thus, entrepreneurial education has become important in tandem with the demand of students seeking business education that can provide the necessary skills to succeed in an increasingly diverse and complex management environment. Entrepreneurial education plays an important role in an uncertain environment because it can develop the insights needed to discover and create opportunities for entrepreneurs and gain the ability to successfully start and manage their own businesses.

Therefore, the university has emphasized the necessity of systematic entrepreneurial education and played a role in conducting professional entrepreneurial education. Many universities are also actively pursuing a variety of educational developments as part of their broader strategy to improve the quality of entrepreneurial courses and programs and to encourage student education and learning. Moreover, they offer many entrepreneurship related courses and programs in purpose of providing students with motivation and confidence in entrepreneurship and a role for social contribution through entrepreneurship (Ogundele, Sambo & Bwoi, 2015).

In some universities, a graduate school of entrepreneurship is run through government-level support to provide systematic and professional entrepreneurial education. The goal of this professional graduate school is to nurture start-up experts who can adapt well to uncertain circumstances. In order to achieve this goal, the schools have provided practical training programs for each start-up stage to differentiate them from programs in existing business schools. The background and purpose of the students who enroll in the entrepreneurship graduate school vary. For example, students go on to the entrepreneurship graduate school for reasons such as the use of information and infrastructure for incubation, the construction of a human network, the preparation for start-up, and the acquisition of a degree. Thus, in many studies on entrepreneurial education, the effectiveness of entrepreneurial education is often measured by the degree of entrepreneurship intention.

Business Educator's Perspective

Educators spend countless hours studying their students in order to find out how they learn best. All students have needs when it comes to how they learn and educators must be able to meet those needs in order to promote successful learning in their classrooms. There is need for increasing the level of achievement of each student and making learning a successful outcome in the classroom. In order to reduce the gap between educators and students about Entrepreneurial Education, it is necessary to analyze the importance and satisfaction of Entrepreneurship curriculum and programmes that students perceived. This generally allows students to improve their knowledge and skills through a well-established Entrepreneurship curriculum and experience. However, most Entrepreneurial Education research focuses on programme design and implementation, and objective evaluation practices by experts and students are still poorly addressed in this field.

Entrepreneurial Education attempts to encourage Entrepreneurs to develop or start their own business. Entrepreneurial Education provides opportunities for knowledge, education, and training to those who are interested in job creation or small business development, learning opportunities, organizing resources at risk, and building a business. In other words, Entrepreneurial Education focuses on the expertise used to discover and commercialize business opportunities. Irrespective of the viable nature of Entrepreneurial Education, many people still do not value it. To some, it is time wasting while others see it as difficult to venture into. In general, individuals are reluctant to take Entrepreneurial career since they consider it to be highly uncertain and risky (Petridou, 2013). However, Entrepreneurship can be promoted through Entrepreneurial Education and training. What this means is that the concept of entrepreneurship can be taught to individuals and students in schools through teaching and training. Instead of holding seminars and inviting people to attend, it can be inculcated into the curriculum and taught in classrooms.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on diversifying the teaching of entrepreneurship education in public universities for self employment: the business educator's perspective in Rivers State. The various concepts were explained in details which include; diversity, entrepreneurial education, issues on resources, talent management, self-employment and educators perspective. The study was concluded that diversifying the teaching of entrepreneurship education will enhance self employment of business education students upon graduation from universities in Rivers State.

Suggestions

1. University authorities should provide non-teaching staff and teaching staff with material resources for teaching Entrepreneurial Education.
2. Entrepreneurial Education should be funded by all stake holders for self-employment in Rivers State.
3. Government should provide human network system for talent management in public universities.
4. University administrators should adopt working administrative style on Entrepreneurial Education for self-employment.

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